

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.2
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914542
 UDC: 332
 JEL: F00, E60

PUBLIC REGULATION OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

ДЕРЖАВНЕ РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ РЕГІОНАЛЬНОГО РОЗВИТКУ

Oleksandr S. Balan, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
 Odesa Polytechnic National University, Odesa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0001-6711-5687
 Email: shurabalan@ukr.net

Maksym V. Voitenko
 Odesa Polytechnic National University, Odesa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0009-0000-8031-6256
 Email: maksvoitenko1980@gmail.com

Dmytro O. Pulcha
 Odesa Polytechnic National University, Odesa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0002-5698-8498
 Email: dima.pulcha@gmail.com

Received 29.10.2023

Balan O.S., Voitenko M.V., Pulcha D.O. Державне регулювання регіонального розвитку. Оглядова стаття.

У цій статті автор розглянув питання державного регулювання регіонального розвитку. Згадуються причини для регулювання – збалансований розподіл ресурсів, економічний розвиток, необхідність локальної фіскальної та інвестиційної політики, а також регулювання торгових та ринкових відносин. Розглядаються заходи державного регулювання. Серед них, наприклад, вкладення коштів в інфраструктуру для стимулювання розвитку регіону та спеціалізація. Такі заходи держрегулювання сприяють забезпеченню соціальної справедливості. Наприклад, створення економічних зон або зон пріоритетного розвитку у нерозвинених регіонах залучить інвестиції та створить робочі місця. Що зменшить рівень нерівності між різними регіонами держави. Висновок – регулювання державного розвитку має значення для зростання економічного розвитку регіону та виправлення дисбалансу у розвитку між регіонами.

Ключові слова: державне регулювання регіонального розвитку, регіональний розвиток, державне регулювання, державна стратегія, Україна, регіон, регіоналізм

Balan O.S., Voitenko M.V., Pulcha D.O. Public Regulation of Regional Development. Review article.

The authors examine the issues of public regulation of regional development in this article. The reasons for regulation are mentioned – a balanced distribution of resources, economic development, the need for local fiscal and investment policies, as well as the regulation of trade and market relations. Measures of public regulation are being considered. Among them, for example, investment in infrastructure to stimulate a region's development, as well as specialization. Such measures of state regulation contribute to ensuring social justice. For example, creating economic zones or zones of priority development in underdeveloped regions will attract investment and create jobs. That will reduce the level of inequality between different regions of the country. The conclusion is as follows: the regulation of state development is important for the growth of the region's economic development and correcting the imbalance in development between regions.

Keywords: public regulation of regional development, regional development, state regulation, state strategy, Ukraine, region, regionalism

In the current conditions, public regulation of regional development is becoming an important tool for ensuring balanced and sustainable regional growth. Ukraine, as a country with diverse regional characteristics, faces the need to develop an effective state strategy and mechanisms of regional regulation in order to achieve harmonious development. The issue is to determine the optimal methods and tools of state intervention to stimulate regional development, avoid inequalities, and ensure equal opportunities for all regions.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Knogler M. and Sekarev O. define regional policy as a set of measures aimed at eliminating differences in economic capacity and living standards between geographically separated parts of the country [25].

The aim of the article is to develop recommendations for improving the public regulation system of regional development in Ukraine. This includes analyzing existing problems, identifying optimal strategies and instruments, and improving the effectiveness of public policy to ensure sustainable and uniform development of the country's regions.

The main part

Public regulation of regional development is an important aspect of the country's policy and is aimed at ensuring a balanced distribution of resources, economic growth and socio-economic development of different regions of the country. Regions in Ukraine have different levels of economic development, access to infrastructure, social protection and other indicators, which require the state's systematic approach to their development.

Public regulation of regional development is of great importance for the country's sustainable

development. This issue has been studied for many years by domestic and Western scholars. For example, this issue was considered in the context of cooperation between Ukraine and the EU in the monographs "Formation of the Public Strategy for Regional Development Management in the Context of Ukraine's European Integration: Essence, Problems and Ways of Improvement" [1] and Kulish "Public Management of Ukraine's Regional Development in the Context of European Integration" [2]. Also, Babinov's work "State Regional Policy and Regional Development: Current Realities of Ukraine and European Experience" [3]. The public strategy for regulating regional development includes the identification of priority areas for the development of each region, taking into account its characteristics and potential. This can be aimed at the development of economic sectors, social infrastructure, education, healthcare, etc.

Regionalism reflects the desire to preserve and maintain the identity and characteristics of a particular region. This may include the development and maintenance of language, culture, traditions and other aspects that distinguish a particular region from others. In the context of public regulation of regional development, regionalism can be taken into account as a factor that affects the strategy and policy of the state with respect to each region separately.

Ukraine, as a multinational and multicultural country, is characterized by the diversity of its regions. In order to achieve the overall national goals, it is important to ensure that the state strategy is focused on preserving and supporting the cultural diversity of each region and increasing the efficiency of economic and social development in each region.

It was also studied in the work of Kovalchuk "Public Administration of the Region's Socio-Economic Development" [4] and in a number of others. For example, in his work Roman Yakovenko "The Objective Necessity and Essence of State Regulation of the Economy" [5]. Bandur in his work "Modern Regional Socio-Economic Policy of the State: Theory, Methodology, Practice" [6] and others.

One of the leading researchers is Michael Porter, a well-known American economist and professor at Harvard Business School. He specializes in competitive analysis and competitiveness, including regional competitiveness. It is reflected in his book "Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analysing Industries and Competitors" [7].

The concept of state regional policy was adopted in Ukraine more than 20 years ago [8].

At the same time, A.V. Kinshchak in his work "State Regional Policy in Ukraine: Terminological Uncertainty" [9] notes that both domestic and foreign scientific literature is characterized by a variety of directions and methodological concepts in modern regional studies, which is largely due to the lack of a clear, unambiguous interpretation of the concept of "region".

The scholar notes that a region, as part of a country's territory, is understood as a significant integral area where a certain number of people live,

where enterprises of various industries and different forms of ownership are located, and where institutions provide normal conditions for people's life, work, education, culture, and communication. The region differs from other regions by a set of natural, historically formed, relatively stable economic, social, and national features. He also adds that a region is a territory within the administrative boundaries of a state characterized by: complexity; integrity; specialization; and manageability, i.e. the presence of political and administrative governing bodies.

State regulation of regional development can be effective only if it is based on clear theoretical ideas about the essence of regional development, about goals set for it and the factors that influence it. According to V. Tsvetkov, reform efforts in Ukraine should be based on theoretically generalized features, peculiarities and trends in the development of social life, and not only on common sense and intuition of practitioners [10]. For a proper understanding of the essence of regional development, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "development" and "growth", on the one hand, and the concept of "regional development" and the related but not identical concepts of "local development", "business prospects", and "economic development", on the other. In the author's scientific article [11] and this paragraph of the dissertation, an attempt is made to explore the understanding of these definitions in the science of public administration and other fields of knowledge and to propose our own definition of regional development in the context of the problem of its state regulation.

Geographers and economists were among the first ones to address the regional development problems. Recently, there has also been a positive trend of interdisciplinary research on regional development problems [12].

Therefore, the region's development should not and cannot be limited to the mechanical growth of individual elements, including economic, social, environmental, etc. As S. Slava and G. Grin rightly point out, growth is not necessarily a panacea for solving social, political, economic, and community problems, and often has unexpected consequences [14].

At the same time, some economists practically equate the concepts of development and growth. They also ignore the fact that improving economic performance usually leads to a deterioration in other indicators of regional development, such as social, environmental, and demographic indicators. Examples of this include the Dnipropetrovsk region, which is one of the most industrially developed in Ukraine, ranks first in terms of its contribution to the national gross domestic product, agricultural and industrial production, exports of goods and budget revenues, but ranks only 24th in the human development index [15]. Certainly, economic development is an important and necessary element of regional development, but it is not self-sufficient.

Of course, the type of regional development can be determined only by the dynamics observed over a

certain period of time. Differentiation of the regional development level, which is to some extent characteristic of all countries without exception, is particularly acute during economic crises and the transition to a market economy. This can be explained by the following groups of reasons:

- the mechanism of market competition is activated, which divides regions according to their competitive advantages and disadvantages, and reveals the different degrees of adaptation to market conditions of regions with different economic structures and different mentalities of the population and authorities;
- the regulatory role of the state is significantly weakened, which is manifested in a reduction of direct state investment in regional development;
- there is a de facto inequality of individual regions in economic relations with the centre, which often has no objective economic basis [16].

There are many reasons for regulating regional development. Among them are:

1) **Balanced distribution of resources:** Public regulation helps to ensure that resources are distributed evenly across regions. This is important to avoid too much accumulation of resources in large cities or regions, while other areas may remain underfunded. Ensuring a level playing field for the development of different regions helps to reduce economic and social inequalities between them.

2) **Economic development:** State regulation of regional development can promote economic growth in regions that are lagging behind. By stimulating investment, supporting entrepreneurship and developing infrastructure in less developed regions, the state can help create new jobs, increase production, and reduce unemployment.

Tofaniuk and Zinchuk note in their work "Public Regulation of Socio-Economic Development of Ukraine's Regions" that the state strategy of regional development should be based on foreign experience, in particular, European development experience. They also emphasize that the main implementers of our state's strategies are currently government agencies, while in European countries the institution of regional development agencies is developed.

However, such an institution eventually began to operate in Ukraine. For example, the Regional Development Agency has been operating in the Odesa region for three years (since 2020). [17] It was established in November 2020 in pursuance of the Law of Ukraine "On the Principles of State Regional Policy" and the Model Regulation on the Regional Development Agency, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on 11 February 2016, No. 258. The Law of Ukraine No. 2389-IX of 09 July 2022 "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine on the Principles of State Regional Policy and the Policy of Restoration of Regions and Territories" amended the Law of Ukraine "On the Principles of State Regional Policy", in particular, to strengthen the role of regional development agencies in the implementation of state regional policy in the regions, expand the circle of founders and co-

founders of the agency, clarify and expand the tasks of the agency (in particular, to hold events on European and Euro-Atlantic integration in the region). It, for example, "initiates the creation of promising investment projects in accordance with the needs of the region and the interest of potential investors".

In the Kyiv region, the Regional Development Agency was established earlier, i.e. in May 2018. Its top three tasks include attracting international technical assistance programmes for communities and entrepreneurs, assisting with the enterprises' relocation, and analysing the region's socio-economic development [18].

The Association of Regional Development Agencies of Ukraine is also currently operating, bringing together 17, and currently 43, regional development agencies (RDAs) from all over Ukraine.

3) **Social justice:** Public regulation of regional development helps to ensure social justice by providing equal opportunities for all citizens regardless of their place of residence. This means that the state should ensure access to quality educational institutions, healthcare services, cultural facilities and other social goods in all the country's regions.

4) **Ensuring sustainable development:** Public regulation of regional development includes the development of strategies and policies aimed at ensuring the regions' sustainable development. This means taking into account environmental, economic and social aspects of development when making decisions on resource use, industrial development and infrastructure.

5) **Strengthening national security:** Equitable regional development is an important element of national security. If some regions remain backward and underfunded, this can lead to economic hardship, social tensions and discontent, which can cause political instability and threaten the security of the country.

Thus, state regulation of regional development is essential to ensure economic growth, social justice, sustainable development and national security. It helps to create favourable conditions for the uniform development of all regions of the country and improve the quality of life of citizens.

It should be noted that to ensure an even distribution of resources between regions, government regulation can use various instruments. The main ones include:

1) **Fiscal policy:** The state can set tax rates, financial distribution mechanisms and public expenditure systems to ensure an even resources distribution across the regions. For example, by applying a progressive taxation scale or designing a system of subsidies for less developed regions, the state can help reduce economic inequalities.

2) **Investment policy:** The state can direct investments to less developed regions, stimulate job creation, develop infrastructure and promote the development of local enterprises. This can be done by providing financial support, reducing tax rates for investors, developing special economic zones, etc.

As Budkin [20] notes in his paper "Main Stages and Regional Peculiarities of Attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Ukraine's Economy", Ukraine is characterized by significant territorial differentiation in attracting investment. For a decade now, a group of investment-attractive regions has been identified in Ukraine. In 2005, according to his data, these 8 administrative units accounted for 66% of capital investments.

3) Regulation of trade relations: The state can establish mechanisms that regulate trade in goods and services between regions to ensure more equal access to markets. For example, it may impose tariffs, quotas or import restrictions on certain goods to support local production in less developed regions.

4) Regulation of market competition: The state can set policies to regulate competition in the market, ensuring that dominant players do not hinder the development of less developed regions. This may include controlling the abuse of monopoly power, promoting the openness of markets to new entrants, and developing antitrust laws.

Of course, in each country, heads of state, parliaments, and governments have a significant impact on regional development, but this paragraph considers the activities of only those bodies that are part of the central executive authorities or are interagency and are specifically authorized to regulate regional development.

Depending on public regulation goals of regional development, European countries have established special ministries or other central executive bodies, various interagency structures, or regional development regulations carried out by non-specialized central executive bodies, which included relevant structural units. Researchers point to these two models of the organizational mechanism of regional development or their combination.

In many Western European countries, non-specialized ministries are responsible for implementing the state policy of regional development. For example, in Germany, this is the Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Housing, in Spain – the Ministry of Economy and Finance, in Italy – the Ministry of Industry. However, they have departments or other structural units that are directly involved in regional development.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of state regulation in ensuring an even distribution of resources may depend on political will, governance and the level of development of the country's institutional system.

Public regulation of regional development can contribute to economic growth in the regions by ensuring a favourable investment climate, stimulating entrepreneurship, supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, developing infrastructure, and improving education and training.

These are some of the ways in which government regulation can contribute to economic growth in the regions:

1) Investment climate: The state can create favourable conditions for investment by ensuring a

stable legal system, property protection and transparent business rules. It is also important to simplify the procedures for establishing businesses and obtaining permits, as well as to reduce bureaucratic burdens.

2) Support for entrepreneurship: Government agencies can provide financial and advisory support to entrepreneurs, for example through loan programmes, grants and incentives for enterprise development. It is also important to provide access to business information and education to help entrepreneurs develop their competencies.

This policy is already being implemented to some extent by regional development agencies.

3) Infrastructure development: The state can invest in transport, energy and information infrastructure, which will help to increase productivity and attract investment. Developing connectivity and communication routes with other regions can also facilitate trade and attract new business opportunities.

4) Human capital development: The state can invest in education and training to ensure the availability of a skilled workforce. This may include support for vocational training, development of the higher education system, creation of training centres and transfer of entrepreneurship knowledge.

5) Regional specialization: The state can promote the development of specific industries or sectors in which the region has a competitive advantage. This can be achieved by stimulating innovation, supporting research and technology development, and facilitating the creation of clusters of enterprises in specific sectors.

These government regulations can help to expand business activity, attract investment and create new jobs in the regions. However, the effectiveness of such regulation depends on the context, specific needs and capabilities of each region, and it is important to develop and implement strategies that take into account local specificities.

Public regulation of regional development also affects social justice by ensuring equal opportunities for all citizens regardless of their place of residence through the following measures:

1) Regional policies formation: The state develops policies aimed at developing specific regions, in particular those that are lagging behind in their socio-economic development. These policies may include financial support, tax incentives, investment incentives and other measures that promote development and improve the quality of life of citizens in backward regions.

2) Infrastructure projects: The state invests in infrastructure projects, such as the construction of roads, bridges, schools, hospitals, water supply and other facilities that improve the quality of life in remote and less developed regions. This ensures equal access to basic services and facilities for all citizens.

3) Regional economic policy: The state can establish special economic zones or priority development zones in less developed regions that attract investment and create new jobs. This helps to

ensure equal opportunities for the local population and helps to reduce regional inequalities.

Public regulation of regional development can be implemented through various measures and instruments. Here are some of the main measures that the state can take to regulate regional development:

- Development of strategic documents and programmes
- Developing and adopting strategies, concepts, and programmes for regional development that define priorities and directions of development for each region.
- Financial support: financial resources provision in the form of subventions, grants, loans and other financial instruments to support economic, social and infrastructure development of the regions.
- Regulation of tax and investment policy: establishing special tax regimes, investment privileges and discounts to support investment and development of certain regions.
- Infrastructure projects: developing and implementing infrastructure projects, such as the

construction of roads, railways, airports, and communications, which contribute to the competitiveness of the regions and attract investment.

- Regulation of land relations: developing and implementing legislation and policies aimed at the rational use of land resources, promoting agricultural and environmentally sustainable development.
- Development of human capital: measures implementation to improve the skills of the regional population, support for education, scientific and cultural institutions.
- Establishment of special economic zones and entrepreneurial incubators: creating favourable conditions for business and industry development in certain regions by establishing special regimes and benefits.
- Regulation of migration processes: managing migration flows, contributing to a balanced distribution of resources and reducing disparities in regional development.

Figure 1. Key State Regulatory Measures
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

These measures may vary depending on specific conditions, country characteristics and regional needs. The state should actively cooperate with local authorities, the public and business to achieve effective regional development.

The state regulation of regional development in different countries is characterized by significant differences, but researchers suggest that all its variants can be reduced to three main ones, which can be combined in certain proportions:

- the state supports the development of advanced and rich regions, which provide for the existence of other regions;
- the state maintains approximately equal living conditions in all regions;

— the state supports only poor regions, while others can develop independently [21].

The necessary conditions for public regulation of regional development are a number of interrelated conditions, in particular, the existence of the public sector of the economy, in relation to which direct state regulation can be carried out, the system of redistribution of a part of the national income through the budget, which is used for the implementation of long-term national programmes, the existence of a developed system of collection and processing of information and training of qualified management personnel. The scientific literature on regional studies has developed different approaches to the disclosure of the content of state regulation of regional development. Most often, the content of state

regulation is considered to be the performance of a certain scope of functions by its subjects [22].

A significant number of researchers interpret state regulation of regional development as a system of economic influences of the state on the situation in the region. Typical is, for example, the position of the authors of the monograph "Regulation of Territorial Development in a Market Economy", who understand public regulation of regional development as a specific influence of interstate, state and local governments on the development of specific territories through financing of targeted programmes, preferential lending and taxation, as well as stimulation of regional development through the use of special budget and extra-budgetary funds, conclusion of interstate agreements to achieve specific social goals. The position expressed in V. Kotylko's textbook on regional economic policy is similar in content.

In terms of social policy, the state implements social programmes aimed at supporting the most vulnerable groups in less developed regions. These may include social protection, education, healthcare, housing subsidies and other measures that promote social justice and ensure equal opportunities for all.

The state can support human development in less developed regions through training programmes, professional development, access to information technology, etc. This helps to ensure equal conditions for education and development for all citizens.

These activities jointly promote social justice by ensuring equal opportunities for all citizens regardless of their place of residence.

Thus, public regulation of regional development is of great importance for increasing the economic development of a region, correcting the imbalance in development between regions and reducing social tensions.

Conclusions

Implementing effective public regulation of regional development is an urgent task for countries, including Ukraine, which faces diversity and inequalities in its regions' development. The public strategy and policy on regional development determine the success in achieving harmonious and sustainable growth.

The study has shown that regional development is a complex process influenced by economic, social, institutional and geographical factors. In order to ensure effective public regulation, it is important to develop a set of strategies and instruments aimed at reducing regional inequalities and creating favourable conditions for the development of all regions.

The main requirement for a national regional development strategy is flexibility and adaptability, as different regions may require different approaches. However, all measures should be based on the principles of equity, equality and sustainable development.

Therefore, public regulation of regional development in Ukraine should be aimed at ensuring a balance between regions, preserving regional identity and creating conditions for the development of all territories of the country. This will require commitment, cooperation and innovative approaches to achieve harmony and sustainable development of the national space.

Abstract

In this article, the author considered the issues of state regulation of regional development. The reasons for regulation are mentioned – a balanced distribution of resources, economic development, the need for local fiscal and investment policies, as well as the regulation of trade and market relations. In Ukraine, back in the early 2000s, the concept of state regional policy was adopted. Separately, the question of what is meant by the word region is considered. According to one of the definitions, this is a part of a significant integral territory where a certain number of the population lives, enterprises of various industries and different forms of ownership are located, institutions that provide normal conditions for people's lives, for work, education, culture, and communication. It is noted that the region differs from other regions by a combination of natural, historically established, relatively stable economic, social, and national features. Measures of state regulation are being considered. Among them, for example, investment in infrastructure to stimulate the development of the region, as well as specialization. Such measures of state regulation contribute to ensuring social justice. For example, the creation of special economic zones or priority development zones in underdeveloped regions will attract investment and create jobs. That will reduce the level of inequality between different regions of the state. The following question was considered, what is the level of state regulation – regional development agencies have already appeared in Ukraine, which allow on the ground to provide more targeted assistance for the development of the region. For example, such an agency in the Kyiv region among the tasks in the top three noted the attraction of international technical assistance programs for communities and entrepreneurs, assistance with the relocation of enterprises, analysis of the socio-economic development of the region. Conclusion – the regulation of state development is important for the growth of the economic development of the region and correcting the imbalance in development between regions within one country.

Список літератури:

1. Формування державної стратегії управління регіональним розвитком в контексті євроінтеграції України: суть, проблеми та шляхи вдосконалення: монографія / В.М. Гончаров, О.А. Трухіна, А.М. Зінченко, А.Є. Пожидаєв, С.В. Захаров, Д.О. Квітковський. Луганськ: Вид-во «Нолідж», 2012. 176 с.
2. Куліш І.М. Державне управління регіональним розвитком України в контексті європейської інтеграції: монографія / І.М. Куліш. Львів: ЛРІДУ НАДУ, 2011. 252 с.
3. Бабінова О.О. Державна регіональна політика і регіональний розвиток: сучасні реалії України та європейський досвід. Київ: Фенікс, 2011. 268 с.
4. Ковальчук В.Г. Державне управління соціально-економічним розвитком регіону: монографія / В.Г. Ковальчук. Харків, Золоті сторінки, 2013. 296 с.
5. Яковенко Р. Об'єктивна необхідність та сутність державного регулювання економіки. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <http://dspace.kntu.kr.ua/jspui/bitstream/123456789/7765/1/424pdf.PDF>.
6. Сучасна регіональна соціально-економічна політика держави: теорія, методологія, практика [Текст] / С.І. Бандур [та ін.]; НАН України, Рада по вивченню продукт. сил України. – К.: РВПС України НАН України, 2002. – 250 с.
7. Porter, M.E. *Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors*. New York: Free Press, 1980. (Republished with a new introduction, 1998).
8. Указ президента України «Про Концепцію державної регіональної політики». Сайт Верховної ради України. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/341/2001#Text>.
9. Кінщак А.В. Державна регіональна політика в Україні: термінологічна невизначеність. Журнал «Державне управління: удосконалення та розвиток». № 6, 2014. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <http://www.dy.nauka.com.ua/?op=1&z=867>.
10. Агенція регіонального розвитку Одеської області. Офіційний сайт. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://rdaod.com.ua/ua/about-page>.
11. Кучеренко О. Концептуальні засади державної регіональної політики України // Вісн. УАДУ. – 2000. – №3. – С. 16-20.
12. Кучеренко Т.В. Чи існує в Україні регіональна виборна влада // Правові проблеми реформування регіональної влади. Матеріали науково – практичної конференції (м. Харків, 12 квітня 2002 р.). – Харків, 2002. – С. 31-34.
13. Ландабасо А. К вопросу о теории регионального развития // Мировая экономика и международные отношения. – 1998. – №3. – С. 133-137.
14. Ландабасо А. К вопросу о теории регионального развития // Федерализм. – 1998. – № 1. – С. 35-42.
15. Ларина Н.И. Задачи и методы региональной политики субъектов федерации в странах рыночной экономики // Регион: экономика и социология. – 1994. – №4. – С. 146-171.
16. Агенція регіонального розвитку Київської області. Офіційний сайт. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://arrko.com.ua/about>.
17. Асоціація агентств регіонального розвитку України. Офіційний сайт. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <http://www.narda.org.ua>.
18. Будкін В.С. Основні етапи та регіональні особливості залучення прямих іноземних інвестицій в економіку України // Регіональна економіка. – 2005. – С. 59-67. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://evnuir.vnu.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/18809/1/43-44.pdf>.
19. Барицька Л.П. Експертні системи аналізу соціально-економічного розвитку регіону: Автореф. дис. канд. екон. наук // Київ. держ. екон. ун-т. – К., 1993. – 21 с.
20. Батанов О.В. Територіальна громада – основа місцевого самоврядування в Україні: Моногр. – К.: Ін-т держави і права ім. В.М. Корецького НАНУ, 2001. – 260 с.
21. Баштанник В. Державна регіональна політика в контексті європейської інтеграції: політичний аспект // Зб. наук. пр. УАДУ. – К., 2000. – Вип. II. – Ч.І. – С. 9-15.
22. Бейкун А. Поняття державного регулювання діяльності обласної ланки агропромислового комплексу як цілісної правової категорії // Право України. – 1999. – №9 – С. 35-39.
23. Кноглер М., Сєкарев О. Ринкова реформа і регіональна політика // Економіка України. – 1995. – № 1. – С. 65.

References:

1. Goncharov, V.M., Trukhina, O.A., Zinchenko, A.M., Pozhidaev, A.Ye., Zakharov, S.V., & Kvitkovskiy, D.O. (2012). *Formation of the State Strategy for Managing Regional Development in the Context of Ukraine's European Integration: Essence, Problems, and Ways of Improvement: Monograph*. Luhansk: Noulidzh Publishing [in Ukrainian].

2. Kulish, I.M. (2011). State Management of Regional Development in Ukraine in the Context of European Integration: Monograph. Lviv: LRIDU NADU [in Ukrainian].
3. Babinova, O.O. (2011). State Regional Policy and Regional Development: Modern Realities of Ukraine and European Experience. Kyiv: Feniks [in Ukrainian].
4. Kovalchuk, V.G. (2013). State Management of Socio-Economic Development of the Region: Monograph. Kharkiv: Zoloti storinky [in Ukrainian].
5. Yakovenko, R. (n.d.). Objective Necessity and Essence of State Regulation of the Economy. Retrieved from: <http://dspace.kntu.kr.ua/jspui/bitstream/123456789/7765/1/424pdf.PDF> [in Ukrainian].
6. Bandur, S.I., et al. (2002). Modern Regional Socio-Economic Policy of the State: Theory, Methodology, Practice. Kyiv: RVPS Ukraine NAN Ukraine [in Ukrainian].
7. Porter, M.E. (1998). Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors. New York: Free Press [in English].
8. Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Concept of State Regional Policy". Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine Website. Retrieved from: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/341/2001#Text> [in Ukrainian].
9. Kinshchak, A.V. (2014). State Regional Policy in Ukraine: Terminological Uncertainty. Journal "Public Administration: Improvement and Development", 6. Retrieved from: <http://www.dy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=867> [in Ukrainian].
10. Regional Development Agency of Odessa Region. Official Website. Retrieved from <https://rdaod.com.ua/ua/about-page> [in Ukrainian].
11. Kucherenko, O. (2000). Conceptual Foundations of State Regional Policy of Ukraine. Visnyk UADU, (3), 16-20 [in Ukrainian].
12. Kucherenko, T.V. (2002). Does Regional Elected Authority Exist in Ukraine? Legal Problems of Regional Governance. Materials of the Scientific and Practical Conference (April 12, 2002, Kharkiv), 31-34 [in Ukrainian].
13. Landabaso, A. (1998). On the Theory of Regional Development. World Economy and International Relations, (3), 133-137 [in Russian].
14. Landabaso, A. (1998). On the Theory of Regional Development. Federalism, (1), 35-42 [in Russian].
15. Larina, N.I. (1994). Tasks and Methods of Regional Policy of Federation Subjects in Market Economy Countries. Region: Economics and Sociology, (4), 146-171 [in Russian].
16. Regional Development Agency of Kyiv Region. Official Website. Retrieved from: <https://arrko.com.ua/about> [in Ukrainian].
17. Association of Regional Development Agencies of Ukraine. Official Website. Retrieved from: <http://www.narda.org.ua> [in Ukrainian].
18. Budkin, V.S. (2005). Main Stages and Regional Features of Attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Ukraine's Economy. Regional Economics, 59-67. Retrieved from: <https://evnuir.vnu.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/18809/1/43-44.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
19. Baritska, L.P. (1993). Expert Systems for Analyzing Socio-Economic Development of the Region: Candidate's Thesis. Kyiv State Economic University [in Ukrainian].
20. Batanov, O.V. (2001). Territorial Community – the Basis of Local Self-Government in Ukraine: Monograph. Institute of State and Law named after V.M. Koretsky of NASU [in Ukrainian].
21. Bashtannik, V. (2000). State Regional Policy in the Context of European Integration: Political Aspect. Collection of Scientific Works UADU, (II), 9-15 [in Ukrainian].
22. Beikun, A. (1999). The Concept of State Regulation of the Activity of the Regional Link of the Agro-Industrial Complex as an Integral Legal Category. Law of Ukraine, (9), 35-39 [in Ukrainian].
23. Knogler, M., & Sekarev, O. (1995). Market Reform and Regional Policy. Economy of Ukraine, (1), 65 [in Ukrainian].

Посилання на статтю:

Balan O.S. Public Regulation of Regional Development / O.S. Balan, M.V. Voitenko, D.O. Pulcha // *Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал.* – 2024. – № 1 (71). – С. 14-21. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/14.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.2. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914542.

Reference a Journal Article:

Balan O.S. Public Regulation of Regional Development / O.S. Balan, M.V. Voitenko, D.O. Pulcha // *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal.* – 2024. – № 1 (71). – P. 14-21. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/14.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.2. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914542.

